

EVALUATION OF IMPACT DAMAGE TO LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The impact damage to glass/ epoxy laminated composites for the leaf spring was evaluated by using the damage mechanics, and the impact damage process was determined by the advanced instrumented impact testing system. The characteristic of damage variation and the quantitative criterion used for assessing the damage have been obtained. The results in this study provide the reliable base of material selection and safety service for engineering application, and also a new practical method for the evaluation of dynamic impact damage of composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

The leaf spring of laminated composite is one of the important application of composite materials to the automobile industry. The high performance for that is demanded because it could be applied impact loading related to the complexity of the load situation. It is , therefore, required to find a method to assess the properties of laminated plate under impact loading. For composites the dynamic fracture phenomenon and failure process are much more complex, the conventional impact tests may not be sufficient for providing data with basic physical significance.

According to the constitution of composites and its failure characteristic, many investigators [1,2,3,4] have reported the fracture failure process in terms of damage mechanics and given some calculation models and damage theories for the laminated plate. However, with the development of composite materials, a more concerned problem is to establish a failure criterion for the engineering application under impact loading. In this paper, the impact damage to glass/epoxy laminated composites for the leaf spring was assessed by using the advanced instrumented impact system. The quantitative criterion used for evaluating the damage and some important parameters have been obtained through analysing and studying the test results for single and multi-specimen.

TEST METHODS

1. Test Setup and Specimen

The test was conducted on a fall weight device, in which the impact energy can be adjusted in the range of 0-150 J and the variable range of impact velocity is at 0.1-4.8 m/sec. A semiconductor strain transducer is mounted on the top of fall weight to record the variation of impact load the deflection of specimen is recorded by the infrared transducer. The whole setup is controlled by the IBM-PC micro computer system. After the specimen has been stricken, the relative curves of P-T(load-time) and P-D (load-deflection) as well as the determined parameters will be recorded and printed out. In addition, the rebounding process and energy of the fall weight can be measured automatically. Fig.1 is the schematic diagram of test setup.

The material of specimen is similar to the component, that is laminated by glass/ epoxy. The nominal size of specimen is 180x25x10 mm (LxWxD). In three point bending,

the span between the supports is 160mm, i.e., the ratio of span to depth is equal to 16. The influence of shear force on impact bending of the specimen may be eliminated.

2. Test Procedure

According to the real load applied to the leaf spring, the specimen is tested in the form of three point bending. For the multi-specimen, each of specimens is impacted once at the different energies to record the P-T, P-D curves and the variation of flexural elastic modulus before and after impact. Keeping the impact velocity in constant, the selected velocity of fall weight is about 4.4 m/sec and the adjustable range of fall weight is from 3-15 kg.

Fig.1 Schematic of test setup.

ANALYSIS OF IMPACT DAMAGE PROCESS

Under impact loading the failure mode of laminated plate is directly dominated by the damage process. The P-T and P-D curves obtained from test, therefore, can obviously use for analysing the damage developing process.

The typical curves of P-T and P-D shown in Fig. 2-6 are obtained from five specimens which are subjected to the different impact energy. Fig. 7-11 are the photographs taken in the impact position to show the damage zone.

For the impact energy of 30.6 J, the P-T curve is presented in the sinuous shape (Fig.2a), there are no obvious damages on the three surfaces of specimen with naked eye. Fig.7 is the photographs of longitudinal section and compressive surface of the specimen. The deflection curve (Fig.2b) shows that there is slight rebounding to the tup after the deflection of specimen has reached the maximum. The energy absorbed by the second specimen is 62.80 J when the contact area between compressive surface and tup appears the impact damage with local delamination as shown in Fig. 8. There are plain stages on the top of P-T and P-D curve and the rebound magnitude is increased (Fig.3).

The impact energy for third specimen is 96.21 J in which the delaminated zone for the compressive portion of specimen is enlarged and developed along the direction of depth (Fig.9). The P-T and P-D curve (Fig.4), are similar to that of second specimen, only the rebound magnitude of tup is much higher. When the impact energy comes to 111.98 J, the compressive surface of fourth specimen, except to the enlargement of delaminated zone, the fibres near the surface are broken due to the bending compression (Fig.10), this leads to that the curve in Fig.5 suddenly falls down when it reaches the maximum point B. However, the remained portion of specimen that has not been damaged continuously stands the load again, i.e., from point C to D on the P-T curve. The capability for bearing load only can be hold before the point D since the damage is severe. At that time the delamination is initiated on the tensile surface of the specimen.

The results of above four specimens are obtained in the case of that the specimens have not been fractured completely. The shapes of P-T and P-D curves in the test results are very similar to that of the curves given by Dorey(1) and C.D.Sims(2). The fifth specimen is fractured by once-impact with the energy of 121.54 J. The tensile surface of specimen appears delaminated zone which propagates from surface to inner and relates to the shear zone DE on the P-T curve (Fig.5). Until the point E is reached, the fibres on the tensile surface are not broken, and the broken region will be deepened along the direction of thickness leading to fracture failure of the specimen (Fig.11).

It is worth notice that the damage variation and propagation process of the specimen subjected to once-impact just are the superposition of the individual damage process for the previous four specimens under different impact energies. In Fig.12 the point B,C,D,E,F,G are in accordance with the characteristic points in Fig.6, it means that it is possible to evaluate the impact damage by use of single specimen test.

a.
b.
Fig.2 P-T and P-D curve under impact energy of 30.62 J

a.
b.
Fig.3 P-T and P-D curve under impact energy of 62.80 J

a.
b.
Fig.4 P-T and P-D curve under impact energy of 96.21 J

Fig.5 P-T and P-D curve under impact energy of 111.98 J

Fig.6 P-T and P-D curve under impact energy of 121.54 J

Fig.7 a. Longitudinal section

b. Compressive surface

Fig.8 a. Longitudinal section

b. Compressive surface

Fig.9 a. Longitudinal section

b. Compressive surface

Fig.10 a. Longitudinal section

b. Compressive surface

Fig.11 a. Longitudinal section

b. Tensile surface

Fig.12 Variation of elastic modulus vs energy G absorbed by specimen.

Fig.13 Impact damage D vs energy G.

CRITERION OF IMPACT DAMAGE

The test results indicate that the elastic modulus of laminated plate is obviously decreased after impact. For this reason, the expression of damage given by Ladeveze [3] has been chosen :

$$D = 1 - (E/E_0) \quad (1)$$

Where E_0 , E and D are the original elastic modulus, the elastic modulus after damage, the damage parameter characterizing the damage, respectively. the test shows that the slight damage will appear when impact energy reaches up

to a certain magnitude that is referred to as the energy threshold of damage initiation and expressed it and damage as G_c and D_c . As the large area damage appears due to the increasing of impact damage, the stiffness and strength begins decreasing rapidly. In that case, the critical values of relative energy G_c and damage D_c have been reached. To insure the component use in safety, the following criterion should be satisfied:

$$D \leq D_c \text{ and } G \leq G_c \quad (2)$$

Fig.14 Impact damage D vs flexural stress

DETERMINATION OF CRITICAL DAMAGE D_c AND IMPACT ENERGY G_c

1. Multi-Specimen Method

Each specimen is impacted by a different energy, and then the curve of damage D vs energy G absorbed by specimen is obtained (Fig.13). From the transition point on the curve the values of G and D can be determined. Moreover, the energy threshold of damage initiation G_{Ic} may be given by drawing-up method. Thus the following results are given

$$G_c = 27.34 \text{ J/cm}^2, D_c = 12.18 \%, G_{Ic} = 7.65 \text{ J/cm}^2$$

There are two transition points on the curve of D vs G. While first point C_1 is reached, the damage is rapidly on the increase. At second point C_2 , the specimen is in the stage of unstable fracture failure. Also after the point C_1 the material strength is on the decrease (Fig.14), the maximum of flexural stress is near the position of point C_1 . For the material tested the critical stress is equal to 727.8 Mpa. In this method, the calculation of energy absorbed by the specimen should subtract the rebound energy. The rebounding process of P-D curve is similar to that of P-D curve obtained by P.J. Hogg[5].

2. Single Specimen Method

It only needs to fracture a specimen using once-impact getting P-T and P-D curves with whole damage process, the critical point can conveniently obtain from the curves. It is found that the first failure point C caused by bending is critical one (Fig.6), in which the critical value G_c is equal to 26.91 J/cm². It indicates that the result of single specimen is well in agreement with that of multi-specimen.

DISCUSSIONS

1. From Fig.13 the damage rates before and after critical point are as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta D / \Delta G &= 6.18 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{J} & G < G_{c1} \\ \Delta D / \Delta G &= 30 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{J} & G_{c1} < G < G_{c2} \\ \Delta D / \Delta G &= 191 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^2/\text{J} & G_{c2} < G \end{aligned}$$

The damage rate at critical point is 5 times larger than that of area before this point, and after the unstable failure point C_2 it is about 30 times than that of the first area ($G < G_c$).

2. The tests show that the dynamic strength is less than the static one, i.e.

$$\sigma_t / \sigma_d = 1.32 \quad (\sigma_t \text{ -- static, } \sigma_d \text{ -- dynamic})$$

3. At the critical point, the energy absorbing ratio is $G_c / G_f = 64.5 \%$ (G_f -- energy to fracture). It indicates that the ability to bear the impact load for this material has been mostly used.